

SOCIAL SCIENCES

FOREIGN POLICY OF THE FIRST PRESIDENT OF GEORGIA - ZVIAD GAMSAKHURDIA AND PECULIARITIES OF THE INTERNATIONAL SITUATION

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Abstract

The presented article discusses the peculiarities of the foreign policy of the first President of Georgia in 1990-1992 and analyzes the legal aspects of this process. Within the framework of the article's research, Zviad Gamsakhurdia's foreign policy is discussed in the context of the political and economic processes taking place in the world in 1990-1992.

Based on empirical materials, we tried to study and analyze the main goal of the foreign policy of the Zviad Gamsakhurdia government, which was expressed precisely in the international recognition of Georgia, which the opposition forces of that time considered one of the unsuccessful aspects of the government's rule in 1990-1992 and named the foreign policy course of the legal government as the reason for the international isolation of the Georgian state.

Research methods: We used empirical, comparative, historical, logical analysis, structural-functional, formal-legal and other methods in the research. With the help of these methods, we studied the materials that we found during the research period. These materials include interviews, report cards, public statements, reports, articles on this issue and research. Based on factual materials, we studied the political and legal issues of the foreign policy of the Georgian state in 1990-1992.

Keywords: Foreign Policy, President, Georgia, Zviad Gamsakhurdia, Russia, USA, Soviet Union.

Introduction: The main goal of Zviad Gamsakhurdia's foreign policy was the international recognition of the Georgian state. Therefore, first of all, we considered it appropriate to consider the foreign policy of Georgia at that time in the context of the political and economic processes taking place in the world in 1980-1990.

It is well known that at the end of the 20th century, namely in 1991, 23 new states emerged in Europe and Asia. This process was triggered by the collapse of the Soviet Union. The new world recognized the independence of the Baltic states, Central Asia, the South Caucasus and other states of Eastern Europe. Those states that gained independence in 1918-1920, 1921 and were then annexed by the Soviet Union reappeared on the world stage, including Azerbaijan, Georgia, Ukraine, Armenia and Belarus. Moldova (then Bessarabia), which existed as a feudal principality in the Middle Ages, was also formed into a republic. In addition, the states that emerged from the Soviet Union - Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Kyrgyzstan - also emerged as independent states, the borders of which were drawn precisely within the bosom of the totalitarian empire of Russia. In Europe, in 1990, the German Democratic Republic, by the will of its people, joined the main German state, the Federal Republic of Germany, and Berlin, which had been divided into two, was reunited and its status as the capital of Germany was returned to it¹.

It is also worth noting the fateful circumstance that at that time, in the mid-1980s, oil prices on the world

market significantly depreciated, which can be considered one of the reasons for the collapse of the Soviet empire. The Soviet government pursued an aggressive policy to suppress national movements in its constituent republics, which resulted in the tragedies of April 9, 1989 in Tbilisi, as well as January 20, 1990 in Baku.

Georgian President Zviad Gamsakhurdia, who clearly and openly opposed the imperialist goals of the USSR, expected support only from Western democratic countries. It should be noted that this was the period when, as a result of the Cold War, the United States and the Soviet Union were fighting for the distribution of power in the world, and the collapse of the socialist camp was the main, primary interest of the United States, and the entire West, including the advanced, democratic states of Central Europe, had to stand by the newly independent and sovereign republics. Zviad Gamsakhurdia's goal was precisely to discuss the national-political development of Georgia in the context of the political events taking place in the world, but he believed that the West was not officially and deliberately showing serious political interest in the republics fighting for independence².

The opinion that representatives of the government of the world's leading state avoided direct support for Georgia is reinforced by their attitude to the tragedy that unfolded in Tbilisi on April 9, 1989. No Western head of state officially condemned the actions of the USSR government and did not comment, except for Senator Halsey, a member of the US Senate Foreign Relations Committee, who not only made a political as-

¹ Gachechiladze Revaz, (2011), "Georgia in the World Context", Archil Sulakauri Publishing House, Tbilisi.

² Gamsakhurdia Konstantine Z., (1995), "Dissident, President, Martyr" Swiss Confederation, Basel.

assessment of the events of April 9, 1989, but also demanded the isolation of the Soviet Union in order to facilitate the Georgian national-liberation movement. This was US Resolution N:110, which implied interest in Georgia and a high standard of support for the national movement³.

The resolution was published in the US government bulletin "Congressman Record" on April 19, 1989 and was immediately printed in the Georgian press.

US Resolution N:110 was an official document. The resolution determined that the US Senate:

1. Supported the struggle of the Georgian people, their demands and demonstrations to gain national independence on their own land.

2. Supported the struggle of the Georgian people for self-determination.

In accordance with the Final Act of the Helsinki Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe, to which the Soviet Union has also signed, the struggle of the Georgian people for human rights is guaranteed by the Vienna Declaration of 1950 on Human Rights and Freedoms, to which the Soviet Union has also signed.

4. Calls on the Soviet government to heed the voice of the Georgian people - to satisfy the legitimate demands of the Georgian people for self-determination and human rights.

After April 9, 1989, Senator Hales presented the draft resolution to the Senate a few days later. Unfortunately, this fact was not followed by a response. It had only the meaning of moral support, because it did not reflect the official support of the United States.

In fact, the same attitude continued in the first half of 1990 during the coming to power of Zviad Gamsakhurdia in Georgia. In the conditions of such a political background in the world, considerable importance was attached to the foreign orientation and course of the national government.

In order to clarify the foreign policy orientation of the Georgian national government, we consider it appropriate to analyze the official international documents adopted by them. Such a document, which concerned the international strategy of the state's development, was the political, legal and economic program of the electoral bloc "Round Table - Free Georgia", the chairman of which was Zviad Gamsakhurdia. Excerpt from the program: "Today, if someone stands by Georgia in the event of a conflict with the Eastern countries, as well as in the event of a conflict with Russia, it will be only the world community and the Western world, to which Georgia will be connected through the Black Sea through Bulgaria and Romania"⁴. Opposition-minded, anti-state-minded forces criticized the Round Table election bloc for the fact that the government's programmatic vision did not openly and clearly talk about a Western orientation, as, for example, in the election platform of the Popular Front. To consider this criticism fair and to assess which party's vision was more correct in terms of the country's foreign policy, or which party's election program was more realistic,

we must consider the events in the world political aspect.

Even after the elections of October 28, 1990, the West's attitude towards Georgia remained virtually unchanged, and it was not surprising that the Georgian government's position also maintained a cautious political agenda. In official texts, speeches, and documents of the highest representatives of the state power, we often encounter such expressions as: "the leading countries of the world." When addressing the country in this form, the government of Zviad Gamsakhurdia, of course, meant Western countries, but did not specifically single out the United States of America. The only reason for this was that they did not want to encourage two opposing forces to further conflict and were maneuvering. The government representatives were also reluctant to call Western countries supporters or allies. This was a fairly realistic assessment of foreign policy for that period and a correct course.

The United States first became interested in Georgia during the referendum on March 31, 1991. President George W. Bush (Sr.) sent former US President Richard Nixon to the country on an unofficial visit. Since the visit was not official, it cannot be considered a state-to-state visit. However, the visit confirmed the increased interest of the United States in Georgia and was considered a preparatory basis for a new relationship between the two states. In addition, the visit also had a political connotation. In particular, before leaving Georgia for Moscow, Nixon visited several polling stations in Tbilisi and got acquainted with the ongoing processes of holding the referendum. By this fact, the US administration made Moscow feel that it respected the aspirations and decision of the Georgian population to declare independence. In addition, Nixon's visit to the polling stations and observation of the referendum would not have given the leaders of the USSR the opportunity to spread false information about the legality of the referendum and its results, and if Moscow had spread false information about the legality of the referendum in Georgia, this would have become a basis for the Russian Federation to doubt and ignore the competence of the United States. As we can see, this unofficial visit had a rather large political load. It is also worth noting that the first serious step towards Georgia was taken by America, thereby bringing the Georgian state into its sphere of interests. Such a political step on the part of America influenced the members of the Georgian government, led by Zviad Gamsakhurdia, and they began to mention the West more actively in their speeches and official state documents⁵.

The positive attitude of the United States towards Georgia is also indicated by the fact that during the visit of former President Nixon, details of a possible meeting between President Zviad Gamsakhurdia and the American President in the near future were discussed. The first President of Georgia often spoke about this in various interviews, which indicates that he openly expressed his real desires and hopes for relations with

³ United States Senate Resolution N:110 on Georgia annexed by the Soviet Union "Georgian Film" July 19, 1989.

⁴ Stephen Jones, (2008), "Georgia: A Political History Since Independence", Iliani Publishing House, Tbilisi.

⁵ Constitution of Georgia, 1978, with amendments and additions 1991: <http://www.matsne.gov.ge>

America and the West. This fact is also confirmed by the fact that one of the Turkish guests paid attention to the American flags on the streets of Tbilisi. Zviad Gamsakhurdia told a Turkish journalist that negotiations were underway in recent days regarding the meeting of the Georgian President with President George W. Bush in Washington. This is another clear example of the leaders of the national government declaring their clear readiness for relations with the United States⁶.

The "Western orientation" of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia is clearly and eloquently outlined in a letter sent to the employees of Georgian Television during his exile in May 1992. Such is Zviad Gamsakhurdia's political vision and orientation towards Western values. Given the geopolitical situation at that time, the President of Georgia could not have taken a more radical position. The President did not hesitate to irritate Moscow, which was avoided by not only the Georgian government, but also the West and all other so-called rebellious republics. The accusation that President Zviad Gamsakhurdia and the freedom-loving government of Georgia did not confront Russia and did not clearly state its position in conversations with their leaders or in speeches is devoid of any real basis. As evidence of this, we will cite the address of the President of the Republic of Georgia, Zviad Gamsakhurdia, to the President of Russia, Mr. Boris Yeltsin, on September 14, 1991. This address shows how carefully Zviad Gamsakhurdia tries to express his words in a way that emphasizes Georgia's independence and does not irritate Russia even more. Moreover, it is clearly visible that he emphasizes the pursuit of a correct foreign policy, the prospects of good-neighboring relations, and at the same time emphasizes the common faith of these two states - the USSR and Georgia. With more blunt statements, it was probably not excluded that Russia would resort to open repressions against the young Georgian state. The Georgian authorities understood this well, that it was necessary to wait, watch, and all goals would be realized. They also heard similar calls from Western leaders. For example, when Zviad Gamsakhurdia was in Moscow with Tengiz Sigua, James Baker, the United States Secretary of State, told him in April 1991 that they had a negative attitude towards the issue of Georgia's independence. At the turn of July-August 1991, first in Moscow and then in Ukraine, US President George W. Bush first expressed a negative attitude towards the Georgian national government fighting for independence⁷. He stated that the US would not support the republics, because he considered it an internal affair of the Soviet Union. Such a position of the US President was disturbing for the Georgian government and the president, and the fact that Georgia was not at the center of attention of the world community became understandable. The United States and the West officially stated that they would not support an independent Georgia. The first precedent for the international isolation of the Georgian government

came from the United States and was conditioned by the international and geopolitical situation at that time. In such a case, any positive or negative position of the Georgian government no longer had any meaning.

The conclusion is that no leader of such a small country, including Zviad Gamsakhurdia, could stand up to the interests of a world power. In such a situation, how should Zviad Gamsakhurdia's government have acted?

We categorically disagree with the widespread opinion in political thought that the indifference shown by America to Georgia at that moment was connected with the political course of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia. At that time, such an attitude of the USA was a result of the international situation. When we discuss the foreign policy of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia, it is undoubtedly necessary to take into account the real circumstance that the Second Republic of Georgia practically existed in the Soviet bosom in 1990-1992, and this explains the fact that Western leaders were unable to clearly state their position. If we rely on the constitutional theory of international law, a newly emerged state becomes a subject of international law only when its independence and sovereignty are recognized by other states. The Republic of Georgia From October 1990 to December 1991, that is, until the formal dissolution of the Soviet Union⁸, no state in the international arena recognized it, except for Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Moldova, which were still part of the Soviet Union at that time, and which were not yet subjects of international law themselves. Romania also recognized the Republic of Georgia (Romania did this because it was also recognizing the independence of Moldova at the same time).

In 1990-1991, Georgia was not admitted to any international organization. The desire of the national authorities of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia to have friendly relations with the West and receive support from the leaders of various countries was not enough. Moreover, the recognition of Georgia as an independent republic in the international arena was beyond the capabilities of the national authorities.

Being outside the international community, not recognizing Georgia's independence, is not the result of Zviad Gamsakhurdia's weak or strong or any quality of foreign policy, but is the result of international relations and the situation of that period and is one of the tragic pages of Georgian history. It takes time to assess the facts so that the objective reality becomes even clearer. Perhaps that is why there are so many mutually exclusive facts and views on the foreign orientation of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia's government⁹.

Conclusion

Often, one of the reasons for the overthrow of the legitimate government in Georgia through a military coup is the foreign policy of the Georgian government in 1990-1992, which has not yet been given a proper legal assessment. However, it should be noted that the

⁶ Constitution of Georgia, 1978, with amendments and additions 1991: <http://www.matsne.gov.ge>

⁷ Shvelidze Dimitri, (2008), "Political Controversies and National Government in Georgia" (1987-1992) Tbilisi.

⁸ Shvelidze Dimitri, (2008), "Political Controversies and National Government in Georgia" (1987-1992) Tbilisi.

⁹ Constitution of Georgia, 1978, with amendments and additions in 1991: <http://www.matsne.gov.ge> (verified 24.06.2023)

main goal of the foreign policy of the government of Zviad Gamsakhurdia was the international recognition of Georgia.

The government that came to power in the Republic of Georgia through the elections of October 28, 1990, strove with all its might to make the Georgian state a subject of international law, but external and internal hostile forces overthrew the legitimate government by armed means and hindered the process of international recognition of Georgia's statehood. It is precisely because of the above circumstances that we believe that a comprehensive study and scientific analysis of Georgia's foreign policy of 1990-1992 should be conducted, the pragmatic purpose of which will be precisely to prevent a military coup d'état with a similar scenario from happening again in today's or tomorrow's Georgia.

It should be noted that in 1990-1991, Georgia was not admitted to any international organization. The desire of President Zviad Gamsakhurdia's national government to have friendly relations with the West and receive support from the leaders of various countries was not enough. Moreover, the recognition of Georgia as an independent republic in the international arena was beyond the capabilities of the national government.

In the process of researching the article, the analysis of Georgia's foreign policy course showed us that Zviad Gamsakhurdia, as the officially elected President of Georgia, did everything possible to achieve international recognition for Georgia, but the political crisis and economic processes taking place in the world at that time, as well as the destructive actions of hostile forces in the country, did not allow the young Georgian state to gain international recognition.

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